

Coping mechanisms of small business owners during Covid-19: Basis in designing a new business strategy model

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to find out the coping mechanism of small business owners during Covid-19, a basis of designing a business strategy model to cope with the negative impact of Covid-19. In this study, there were 161 business owners participated from different industries such as service, merchandising and manufacturing. The response of the business owners to the different coping strategies that were categorized as Financial Management Coping Strategy, Operational Management Coping Strategy, and Expenses Management Coping Strategy has been evaluated. Furthermore, the level of the coping strategy per nature of business, form of business, number of employees, tenure of the business, and ownership of the store were examined. Finally, the perceived effectiveness of these coping mechanism as per balancing expenses, cash flow, financial stability, business continuity and payables were evaluated. The hypothesis about the difference in coping strategies on the different nature of the business, form of the business, number of employees, tenure of the business and the ownership of the store were also validated.

Keywords: Coping mechanisms; small business owners; Covid-19; business strategy model.

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Introduction

Covid-19 has a devastating effect to people from different walks of life all over the world, but what distinguishes it from other catastrophic events? It has brought a significant change to peoples' lives and business activities not only in the Philippines, but globally. The Philippine government took immediate action to control the Covid-19 situation through the implementation of strict lockdown from mid-March to the end of May 2020 in the National Capital Region and high-risk provinces. This caused a tremendous crisis to small businesses as well as to large businesses. It is noticeable that Covid-19 caused a global shock, which causes layoffs, loss of income, reduction of supply and productivity, and worsened economic vision. Some businesses closed their operations temporarily, and other businesses closed permanently due to extreme vagueness of the path, duration, magnitude, and impact of the pandemic.

According to Ferguson et al. (2020), pandemics are not unique and have happened at various points in human history. This is especially because animal viral infections are emerging more frequently (Madhav et al., 2017). Many studies, including Garrett (2007), Keogh-Brown et al. (2008), and most recently Madhav et al. (2017) and Fan et al. (2018), argued that a large-scale global pandemic was inevitable given the growth in pandemic frequency. Ferguson et al. (2020) said that the COVID-19 Response Team from Imperial College London asserted that COVID-19 is the most severe outbreak since the 1918 Spanish Influenza pandemic.

According to the study of Herbane (2019), small businesses were the ones affected the most in the pandemic. Compared to big and well-established businesses, the small businesses showed high reactions to crisis partly due to limited resources and weaker market positioning. Despite this pandemic, there are small businesses that are operating for the purpose of supplying the needs for their families, and they are not ready for a long crisis as the Covid-19 pandemic. Furthermore, despite the undeniable negative impact of Covid-19 to all the major industries in the Philippines, or even in other countries, business owners still strive to survive hoping that soon they will overcome this pandemic.

It is noticeable that small businesses and big businesses are currently coping with the effect of Covid-19. Manufacturing industries shifted producing non-essential products to essential products. Miller (2020) said that, in an effort to combat Covid-19, the London-based boutique liquor firm 58 Gin shifted its focus from small-batch gin distillation to large-batch hand sanitizer production. According to Inquirer.net BrandRoom (2020), in the Philippines, Reliance, a clothing maker and exporter, and EMS, a firm that subcontracts electronics, semiconductors, and medical services, converted buildings to make protective gear. Destileria Limtuaco, a producer of spirits, altered some of its manufacturing processes to produce ethyl alcohol, an essential component of hand sanitizers. Additionally, San Miguel Corporation transformed Ginebra San Miguel Inc., its spirits division, into a 24/7 disinfection manufacturing facility at its Cabuyao plant.

Trading companies jointly worked with online shopping business instead of selling the traditional way as some of them tied up with electronic commerce like Shopee or Lazada. Also, service industries are obviously experiencing a very devastating effect of Covid-19. However, some service companies still tried to cope by providing services through online platform. Despite the damage caused by the pandemic, business owners are optimistic to do everything to cope from the effect of this crisis.

With these given effects brought by the Covid-19 pandemic, the researcher was inspired to conduct a study in order to find out the business strategies used by small business owners to cope with the effect of Covid-19 and design a new business strategy model and propose this model hoping to serve as a helpful reference for the business enthusiasts.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to assess the coping mechanism of businesses at this time of pandemic. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following:

1. What is the demographic profile of respondents based on the following:
 - 1.1 Nature of the Business;
 - 1.2 Form of the Business;
 - 1.3 Number of Years in the Business;
 - 1.4 Number of Employees; and
 - 1.5 Ownership of the Store?
2. What is the level of operational management coping strategy per demographic profile?
3. What is the level of financial management coping strategy per demographic profile?
4. What is the level of expenses management coping strategy per demographic profile?
5. What is the perceived effectiveness of each coping strategy per target area such as:
 - 5.1 Balancing expenses
 - 5.2 Cash flow

- 5.3 Financial stability
 - 5.4 Business continuity; and
 - 5.5 Payables?
6. Is there a significant difference from the result of the coping strategies when grouped as per demographic profile?
 7. What business strategy model can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the coping strategies and demographic profile when grouped as per nature of business, form of business, number of years in the business, number of employees, and ownership of the store.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-quantitative method of research to find out the demographic profile of the respondents; to determine the strategies used by small business owners in coping with the effect of Covid-19; and to determine the perceived effectiveness of each coping strategy per target area such as balancing expenses, cash flow, financial stability, business continuity, and payables. ANOVA was used to determine the significant difference of the business owners' coping strategy when grouped according to demographic profile.

Sampling

The respondents of this study are composed of 161 business owners in Bacoor, Cavite, which consist of 25 out of 73 barangays. In each barangay, it has small enterprises that caters services, provides goods and manufactures products. Respondents were surveyed in March and April of 2021 with customized questionnaires to collect data on the business tactics employed by entrepreneurs in the COVID-19 pandemic. Based on the respondents' availability, the researcher generated 161 respondents using the purposive sample technique.

In this study, purposive sampling technique was used in determining the respondents' nature of business, form of the business, ownership of the store, number of year operating the business, number of employees, and the strategies they made to cope with the effect of Covid-19. The respondents are those business owners with employees of not more than 20. Their business stores are located in the barangays near Mambog, Bacoor, Cavite, and the business is operating for the past three years and above.

Instruments

The researcher developed questionnaires from the various concepts of business strategies covering operational management, financial management, and expenses management. In order to get the desired data from the business owners, the researcher used survey questionnaires as the major instrument composed of four parts: profiles of the respondents, checklist, a ranking scale of the different business strategies that used during Covid-19 pandemic, and a ranking scale of the effectiveness in the target areas of balancing expenses, cash flow, financial stability, business continuity, and payables.

The first part of the questionnaire is about the business owner's profile such as nature of the business, form of the business, number of years in the business, number of employees, and ownership of the store. The second part is a checklist composed of eight items about the challenges being experienced by business owners at the time of pandemic. The third part is a 30-item 5-point Likert scale that measures the following: Items 1, 4, 7, 10, 13, 16, 19, 22, 25, and 28 are items that measure operational management coping strategy. Items 8, 11, 14, 17, 20, 23, 26, and 29 are items that measure financial management coping strategy. Items 2, 5, 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21, 24, 27, and 30 are items that measure expenses management coping strategy.

The fourth part is a 15-item questionnaire. Per coping strategy, respondents rated using 5-point Likert scale to measure effectiveness in the target areas of balancing expenses, cash flow, financial stability, business continuity, and payables. The 5-point Likert Scale used in the questionnaire measures the degree of agreement of the respondents based on the following numerical and verbal descriptions and interpretations. The arbitrary scale was constructed having a uniformed difference in each interval. The test questionnaire was validated by research experts and panelists. It underwent a reliability scoring with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.881 for operational management coping strategy, 0.930 for financial management coping strategy, and 0.769 for expenses management coping strategy.

Data Collection

The data were collected with the use of online survey form. The online survey form was forwarded to the business owner-respondents through the help of some barangay captains in forwarding the link to the business owners in its community. Some friends also helped in forwarding the online survey link to business owners in the area. Respondents were instructed to answer the survey based on their experience. The researcher assured the respondents that the data gathered would be treated with utmost confidentiality. The data were collected within 30 days.

The results were tallied and tabulated. Frequency count with corresponding percentage was computed. Results were interpreted using weighted mean and standard deviation. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the significant difference between the coping strategies when grouped according to nature of business, form of business, number of years operating the business, number of employees and the ownership of the store. If the p-value is <0.05 , reject hypothesis, otherwise fail to reject hypothesis, there being no significant difference (Statistics Solutions, 2013). To draw findings, this study used data from both primary and secondary sources. While material from books, journals, and electronic sources is found in secondary sources, primary sources involve gathering data directly from people through surveys.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of respondents. For the nature of business, the 161 business owner-respondents encompassed 24 or 15% of the respondents from manufacturing industries, 77 or 48% from merchandising industries, and 60 or 37% from service industries. This shows that majority of the respondents are into buying and selling of goods. According to Bacoor Government Center (2015), majority of the industries in Bacoor are into retail and merchandising.

For the form of business, 126 or 78% of the respondents are sole proprietorships, 27 or 17% of the respondents are partnerships, and eight (8) or 5% of the respondents are cooperatives. This indicates that majority of the business owner-respondents created and formed their businesses only by themselves or individually. Though forming cooperative business is easy, operating it is very challenging because it needs board of directors to manage it.

Table 1. Frequency distribution of respondents (N=161)

Demographic Profile	Variables	Frequency	Percent (%)
Nature of business	Manufacturing	24	15
	Merchandising	77	48
	Service	60	37
Form of the business	Sole proprietorship	126	78
	Partnership	27	17
	Cooperatives	8	5
Number of years in the business	More than 15	13	8
	13 to 15	12	7
	10 to 12	29	18
	7 to 9	30	19
	4 to 6	29	18
	1 to 3	48	30
Number of employees	No employee	8	5
	1 to 5	103	64
	6 to 10	37	23
	11 to 15	7	4
	More than 15	6	4
Ownership of the store	Owned	66	41
	Rented	95	59

For number of years operating the business, 13 or 8% of the respondents are operating for more than 15 years, 12 or 7% of the respondents are operating for 13 to 15 years, 29 or 18% of the respondents are operating for 10 to 12 years, 30 or 19% of the respondents are operating for seven to nine years, 29 or 18% of the respondents are operating for four to six years, and 48 or 30% of the respondents are operating for one to three years. This indicates that majority of the business owner-respondents which is 48 out of 161 are newbies in the business industries when the Covid-19 had exploded, and they were still on the stage of introducing their business or products to the market. It is the crucial stage in business life cycle because business owners are still creating a demand for their products.

For number of employees, eight (8) or 5% of the respondents declared that they do not have employees, 103 or 64% of the respondents have one to five employees, 37 or 23% of the respondents have six (6) to 10 employees, seven (7) or 4% of the respondents have 11 to 15 employees, and six (6) or 4% of the respondents have more than 15 employees. This indicates that most of the business owners have employed one to five helpers or workers to help them in the operation of the business. Only eight (8) out of 161 are considered as the so-called ‘self-employed’ business owners, because they do not have any employee. For ownership of the store, 69 or 43% of the respondents owns business stores, while 92 or 57% of the respondents rents business stores. This indicates that majority of the business owner-respondents rent their store facilities.

Table 2 shows the mean score for operational management coping strategy per demographic profile of business owner-respondents. For the nature of business in general, the weighted mean score is 4.47 (SD 0.86) with a verbal description of “Strongly agree”, and a verbal interpretation of “Very high” operational management coping strategy. Among the nature of the business, the service industries obtained a weighted mean of 4.17 (SD 0.98) with a verbal description of “agree” and a verbal interpretation of “high” operational management coping strategy compared to merchandising and manufacturing with a weighted mean of 4.68 (SD 0.71) and 4.57 (SD 0.79) respectively, with a verbal description of “strongly agree” and verbal interpretation of “very high” operational management coping strategy. This may indicate that there are some operational management coping strategies that are not being used by service industries, while the merchandising and manufacturing industries are using. This is simply because the nature of their operations are not the same.

Table 2. Mean score of operational management coping strategy

Demographic Profile	Variables	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
Nature of business	Manufacturing	4.68	0.71	Strongly agree	Very high
	Merchandising	4.57	0.79	Strongly agree	Very high
	Service	4.17	0.98	Agree	High
Form of the business	Sole proprietorship	4.45	0.88	Strongly agree	Very high
	Partnership	4.57	0.73	Strongly agree	Very high
	Cooperatives	4.49	0.83	Strongly agree	Very high
Number of years in the business	More than 15	4.56	0.78	Strongly agree	Very high
	13 to 15	4.70	0.71	Strongly agree	Very high
	10 to 12	4.62	0.69	Strongly agree	Very high
	7 to 9	4.84	0.49	Strongly agree	Very high
	4 to 6	4.30	1.01	Strongly agree	Very high
	1 to 3	4.18	0.96	Agree	High
Number of employees	No employee	3.94	1.00	Agree	High
	1 to 5	4.43	0.88	Strongly agree	Very high
	6 to 10	4.79	0.59	Strongly agree	Very high
	11 to 15	4.17	0.83	Agree	High
	More than 15	4.37	0.85	Strongly agree	Very high
Ownership of the store	Owned	4.26	0.92	Strongly agree	Very high
	Rented	4.61	0.81	Strongly agree	Very high
Overall weighted mean		4.47	0.86	Strongly agree	Very high

Legend: 1.00-1.79 – Strongly disagree, Very low; 1.80-2.59 – Disagree, Low; 2.60-3.39 – Neutral, Average; 3.40-4.19 – Agree, High; 4.20-5.00 – Strongly agree, Very high

For the form of business, the table above reveals a weighted mean of 4.48 (SD 0.86) with verbal description of “strongly agree” and verbal interpretation of “very high” operational management coping strategy. This indicates that regardless of the number of the owners of a business, the business owner-respondents strongly agree that operational management coping strategy is very highly effective as reflected on the weighted mean score of 4.45, 4.57 and 4.49 for sole proprietorship, partnership and cooperatives respectively.

For the number of years in the business, the table above also shows a weighted mean, as a whole, of 4.47 (SD 0.86) with a verbal description of “strongly agree” and a verbal interpretation of “very high” operational management coping strategy. Respondents who are in their seventh to ninth year of operation obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.84 (SD 0.49), and those who are on the stage of introducing their business which is between one to three years’ operating got the lowest weighted mean of 4.18 (SD 0.96) with a verbal description of “agree” and a verbal interpretation of “high” operational management coping strategy. This indicates that during the start-up stage of a business, which is within three years, operation strategies are very challenging since business owners are on the stage of establishing their market demand when coincidentally Covid-19 arrived.

For the number of employees, the table above also reveals the overall weighted mean is 4.47 (SD 0.86) with verbal description of “strongly agree” and verbal interpretation of “very high” operational management coping strategy. Among the ranges of number of employees, those who employed six (6) to 10 employees obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.79 (SD 0.59) with verbal description of “strongly agree” and verbal interpretation of “very high” operational management coping strategy, while those who have no employees obtained the lowest weighted mean of 3.94 (SD 1.0) which described verbally as “agree” and verbally interpreted as “high” operational management coping strategy. Two heads are undoubtedly preferable to one, in the words of Richard Branson, and by working together as a team and pooling ideas, there is a greater likelihood of developing a plan that will enable the company to overcome a setback (Lewis, n.d.).

For the ownership of the store, the table above also reveals a weighted mean of 4.47 (SD 0.87) as a whole which described verbally as “strongly agree” and interpreted as “very high” operational

management coping strategy. This indicates that regardless of the possession of the store, the use of operational management coping strategies is very effective. In general, majority of the operational management coping strategies being used by the business owner-respondents are in a very high level, which means that these strategies are being regarded as very important by the business owner-respondents in running their businesses.

Table 3. Mean score of financial management coping strategy

Demographic Profile	Variables	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
Nature of business	Manufacturing	4.52	0.83	Strongly agree	Very high
	Merchandising	4.49	0.85	Strongly agree	Very high
	Service	3.96	0.98	Agree	High
Form of the business	Sole proprietorship	4.32	0.92	Strongly agree	Very high
	Partnership	4.44	0.91	Strongly agree	Very high
	Cooperatives	4.22	0.91	Strongly agree	Very high
Number of years in the business	More than 15	4.48	0.82	Strongly agree	Very high
	13 to 15	4.00	0.63	Agree	High
	10 to 12	4.50	0.83	Strongly agree	Very high
	7 to 9	4.70	0.73	Strongly agree	Very high
	4 to 6	4.30	0.94	Strongly agree	Very high
	1 to 3	3.90	0.94	Agree	High
Number of employees	No employee	3.66	0.83	Agree	High
	1 to 5	4.27	0.94	Strongly agree	Very high
	6 to 10	4.69	0.69	Strongly agree	Very high
	11 to 15	4.02	0.99	Agree	High
	More than 15	3.92	0.98	Agree	High
Ownership of the store	Owned	4.11	0.94	Agree	High
	Rented	4.48	0.87	Strongly agree	Very high
Overall weighted mean		4.33	0.92	Strongly agree	Very high

Legend: 1.00-1.79 – Strongly disagree, Very low; 1.80-2.59 – Disagree, Low; 2.60-3.39 – Neutral, Average; 3.40-4.19 – Agree, High; 4.20-5.00 – Strongly agree, Very high

Table 3 shows the mean score for financial management coping strategy as per demographic profile. For the nature of the business, the overall weighted mean is 4.31 (SD 0.93) with verbal description of “strongly agree” and verbal interpretation of “very high” financial management coping strategy. Among the three nature of business, services industries had the lowest mean score of 3.96 (SD 0.98), which is verbally described as “agree” and verbally interpreted as “high” financial management coping strategy. Since the nature of operating service industries does not require inventory stacking, it indicates that the service industries had lesser financing needs as compared to merchandising and manufacturing with a weighted mean of 4.52 (SD 0.83), and 4.49 (SD 0.85) respectively, which is verbally described as “strongly agree”, and verbally interpreted as “very high” financial coping strategy.

For the form of business, the table shows the overall weighted mean score of 4.33 (SD 0.92), which is verbally described as “strongly agree”, and verbally interpreted as “very high” financial management coping strategy. It reveals that regardless of the number of owners who formed a business, the three forms of business obtained a weighted mean scores of 4.32 (SD 0.92), 4.44 (SD 0.91) and 4.22 (SD 0.91) for sole proprietorship, partnership and cooperatives respectively, which are all verbally described as “strongly agree”, and verbally interpreted as “very high” financial management coping strategies. This indicates that financial management is very much effective to all business owners during the time of pandemic.

For the number of years, it shows an overall weighted mean of 4.34 (SD 0.91) with verbal description of “strongly agree”, and verbal interpretation of “very high” financial management coping strategy. Among the ranges of years of operation, those business owner-respondents who operated between 7 to 9 years obtained the highest mean score of 4.70 (SD 0.73), which is verbally described as “strongly agree”, and verbally interpreted as “very high” financial management coping mechanism. Those who are operating in between one to three years obtained the lowest mean score of 3.90 (SD 0.94), which is verbally

described as “agree”, and verbally interpreted as “high” financial management coping strategy. This indicates that during the launch phase of the business, funding the operation is crucial, the revenue is low, and financial risk is very high due to Covid-19.

For the number of employees, as a whole, the weighted mean score is 4.31 (SD 0.92) with verbal description of “strongly agree” and verbal interpretation of “very high” financial management coping strategy. Among the ranges of number of employees, those businesses who have no employee, have 11 to 15 employees, and have more than 15 employees obtained a mean score of 3.66 (SD 0.83), 4.02 (SD 0.99), and 3.92 (SD 0.98) respectively, which verbally described as “agree”, and verbally interpreted as “high” financial management coping strategy. Those businesses who have one to five employees and six (6) to 10 employees obtained a mean score of 4.27 (SD 0.94), and 4.69 (SD 0.69) respectively, with a verbal description of “strongly agree” and verbal interpretation of “very high” financial management coping strategy. This demonstrates that those who have one to five and six to ten employees are strategizing to manage their finances effectively in order to support the funding of the operation of the business despite the economic crisis due to Covid-19.

For the ownership of the store, it shows an overall weighted mean score of 4.33 (SD 0.92) with verbal description of “strongly agree” and verbal interpretation of “very high” financial management coping strategies. However, those who own stores obtained a weighted mean score of 4.11 (SD 0.94), verbally described as “agree” and interpreted as “high” financial management coping strategy, as compared to those who rent stores with a weighted mean score of 4.48 (SD 0.87), which is verbally described as “strongly agree” and interpreted as “very high” financial management coping strategy. This indicates that those who are renting stores are strategizing to manage their finances more than those who own stores, because they are paying their monthly rentals.

In terms of financial management coping strategies, it shows that these strategies are in a very high level, which means that these strategies are being regarded as very important by the business owner-respondents in running their businesses. Financial management is indeed more difficult during the pandemic. As shown in Philippine enterprise survey conducted by the Asian Development Bank from April to May 2020, microenterprises faced the most serious shortage of working capital. Also, based on the result of case study of Chowdhury et al. (2020), the COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in a deficit of working capital, which has made it challenging to pay operating expenses.

Table 4 shows the mean score for expenses management coping strategy as per demographic profile. For the nature of the business, it reveals that expenses management coping strategy is very high with an overall weighted mean score of 4.94 (SD 0.31), which verbally described as “strongly agree”. As shown on the table, the three nature of businesses got a weighted mean of 4.97 (SD 0.24), 4.95 (SD 0.32), and 4.89 (SD 0.42) for merchandising, manufacturing and service industries respectively. This indicates that whatever nature of operation of the business is, expenses should be managed efficiently.

For the form of business, it shows an overall weighted mean score of 4.48 (SD 0.77) with a verbal description of “strongly agree” and verbal interpretation of “very high” expenses management coping strategy. The weighted mean of each form of business, 4.45 (SD 0.81) for sole proprietorship, 4.59 (SD 0.65) for partnership, and 4.53 (SD 0.63), which verbally described as “strongly agree” and interpreted as “very high” expenses management coping strategy shows very close results. This indicates that, regardless of the number of owners in a business, expenses are to be managed properly.

For the number of years in business, the overall weighted mean is 4.48 (SD 0.82) with verbal description of “strongly agree” and interpreted as “very high” expense management coping strategy. Among the range of the number of years operating the business, those businesses who are operating within one to three years obtained the least weighted mean of 4.18 (SD 0.82), which is verbally described as “agree”, and interpreted as “high” expense management coping strategy. Since these businesses are in their launching stage, expenses are very high. One of the most challenging parts of the life cycle of a business is managing expenses at the launching stage of business because creating demand cost much.

Table 4. Mean score of expenses management coping strategy

Demographic Profile	Variables	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
Nature of business	Manufacturing	4.97	0.24	Strongly agree	Very high
	Merchandising	4.95	0.32	Strongly agree	Very high
	Service	4.89	0.42	Strongly agree	Very high
Form of the business	Sole proprietorship	4.45	0.81	Strongly agree	Very high
	Partnership	4.59	0.65	Strongly agree	Very high
	Cooperatives	4.53	0.63	Strongly agree	Very high
Number of years in the business	More than 15	4.53	0.74	Strongly agree	Very high
	13 to 15	4.69	0.68	Strongly agree	Very high
	10 to 12	4.63	0.64	Strongly agree	Very high
	7 to 9	4.78	0.59	Strongly agree	Very high
	4 to 6	4.42	0.85	Strongly agree	Very high
	1 to 3	4.18	0.82	Agree	High
Number of employees	No employee	4.06	0.77	Agree	High
	1 to 5	4.42	0.82	Strongly agree	Very high
	6 to 10	4.75	0.59	Strongly agree	Very high
	11 to 15	4.21	0.78	Agree	High
	More than 15	4.45	0.73	Strongly agree	Very high
Ownership of the store	Owned	4.30	0.80	Strongly agree	Very high
	Rented	4.60	0.75	Strongly agree	Very high
Overall weighted mean		4.48	0.78	Strongly agree	Very high

Legend: 1.00-1.79 – Strongly disagree, Very low; 1.80-2.59 – Disagree, Low; 2.60-3.39 – Neutral, Average; 3.40-4.19 – Agree, High; 4.20-5.00 – Strongly agree, Very high

For the ownership of the store, it reveals that the overall weighted mean is 4.48 (SD 0.78), which is verbally described as “strongly agree” and interpreted as “very high” expense management coping strategy. Regardless of the possession of the store, whether rented or owned, business owners used the expense management coping strategy highly.

In terms of expenses management coping strategies, it shows that these strategies are in a very high level, which means that these strategies are being regarded as very important by the business owner-respondents in running their businesses. This is corroborated by a study conducted in 2020 by Bartik et al., which found that the effects of COVID-19 on small businesses already resulted in significant disruption and that many of these companies had low cash reserves at the start of the pandemic. As a result, these companies will need to make significant cost reductions, take on more debt, or file for bankruptcy. Additionally, according to Fairlie (2020), business owners have already lost a significant amount of revenue from their enterprises due to significant losses in commercial activity in April 2020 and ongoing losses in May and June 2020, even though the amounts lost were lower.

Table 5 shows the perceived effectiveness of each coping strategy per target area. Under the operational management coping strategy, the weighted mean score across target areas such as balancing expenses, cash flow, financial stability, business continuity and payables are greater than 4.20 with a verbal description of "Strongly Agree" and verbal interpretation of "Operational Management is very effective in each target areas". This indicates that reducing production of goods, reducing inventory stacking, shortening operation hours, arranging skeletal workforce, using alternative ways to market business such as utilizing online media platform, tapping e-delivery services and following the health protocols set by the government are very effective coping strategies to maintain earning more revenue than incurring expenses, to prolong working capital, to secure finances, to sustain business operation during pandemic and to meet obligations when due.

Millions of enterprises face an experiential threat (Chen et al., 2021) due to the impact of Covid-19 pandemic. It is critical to comprehend how economic crises are recovered from. According to Carlsson-Szlezak et al. (2020), it is not anticipated that the COVID-19 economic recovery will be simple. This is

because it is expected that social distancing policies and lockdowns will have far greater negative consequences on employment.

Table 5. Perceived effectiveness of each coping strategy per target area

Coping Strategy	Target Areas	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
Operational Management	Balancing Expenses	4.59	0.65	Strongly agree	Very effective
	Cash Flow	4.57	0.66	Strongly agree	Very effective
	Financial Stability	4.57	0.69	Strongly agree	Very effective
	Business Continuity	4.57	0.67	Strongly agree	Very effective
	Payables	4.50	0.73	Strongly agree	Very effective
Overall weighted mean		4.56	0.68	Strongly agree	Very effective
Financial Management	Balancing Expenses	4.54	0.74	Strongly agree	Very effective
	Cash Flow	4.58	0.67	Strongly agree	Very effective
	Financial Stability	4.61	0.66	Strongly agree	Very effective
	Business Continuity	4.64	0.62	Strongly agree	Very effective
	Payables	4.58	0.70	Strongly agree	Very effective
Overall weighted mean		4.59	0.68	Strongly agree	Very effective
Expenses Management	Balancing Expenses	4.56	0.69	Strongly agree	Very effective
	Cash Flow	4.57	0.69	Strongly agree	Very effective
	Financial Stability	4.55	0.72	Strongly agree	Very effective
	Business Continuity	4.57	0.71	Strongly agree	Very effective
	Payables	4.56	0.73	Strongly agree	Very effective
Overall weighted mean		4.56	0.71	Strongly agree	Very effective

Legend: 1.00-1.79 – Strongly disagree, Very ineffective; 1.80-2.59 – Disagree, Ineffective; 2.60-3.39 – Neutral, Average; 3.40-4.19 – Agree, Effective; 4.20-5.00 – Strongly agree, Very effective

For financial management coping strategy, the weighted mean score across target areas such as balancing expense, cash flow, financial stability, business continuity, and payables is greater than 4.20 with a verbal description of "Strongly Agree" and verbal interpretation of "Financial Management is very effective in each target areas". This indicates that using personal savings to cover the shortage of working capital, delaying payment of bills with proper negotiation with the creditors, intensifying collections through offering discounts, leveraging friends and relatives and borrowing money from financial institutions are very effective coping strategies to maintain earning more revenue than incurring expenses, to prolong working capital, to secure finances, to sustain business operation during pandemic and to meet obligations when due. Financial management challenges are not rare for small business owners. Nanavati (2017) asserts that small business owners ought to endeavor to uphold the integrity and productivity of their company's financial resources to accomplish strategic goals and optimize return on investment.

For expenses management coping strategy, the weighted mean score across target areas such as balancing expense, cash flow, financial stability, business continuity, and payables is greater than 4.20 with a verbal description of "Strongly Agree" and verbal interpretation of "Expenses Management is very effective in each target areas". This indicates that reducing capital investment, minimizing the usage of utilities, controlling the daily operating expenses, considering cheaper products as substitute to the main product ingredients or materials used in the operation of the business, and deliberating expenses are very effective coping strategies to prolong working capital, to secure finances, to sustain business operation during pandemic and to meet obligations when due.

Managing expenses is not easy. According to Sood (2020), a line by line review of expenses is critical to see where you can shave costs over the short time. Lowering expenditures to reflect reduced activity can help businesses break even. In terms of the coping strategies being used per target area, it reveals that business owner-respondents perceive these strategies as very effective, since they have proven already that the strategies have been helpful to them.

Table 6 shows the test for significant difference per coping strategy per demographic profile. For ownership of the store, the computed p-value across coping strategies is less than .05 alpha level, this means

that there is significant difference, and null hypothesis is rejected. For nature of the business, the computed p-value across coping strategies is less than .05 alpha level, this means that there is significant difference and null hypothesis is rejected.

For form of the business, the computed p-value across coping strategies is greater than .05 alpha level, this means that there is no significant difference and null hypothesis failed to reject. For number of years in the business, the computed p-value across coping strategies is less than .05 alpha level, this means that there is significant difference and null hypothesis is rejected. For number of employees in the business, the computed p-value across coping strategies is less than .05 alpha level, this means that there is significant difference and null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 6. Test for significant difference

Demographic Profile	Coping Strategy	p-value	Ho Decision	Significance
Ownership of the Store	Operational Management	.000	Reject	Significant
	Financial Management	.000	Reject	Significant
	Expenses Management	.000	Reject	Significant
Nature of the Business	Operational Management	.000	Reject	Significant
	Financial Management	.000	Reject	Significant
	Expenses Management	.000	Reject	Significant
Form of the Business	Operational Management	.173	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
	Financial Management	.173	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
	Expenses Management	.173	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Number of Years in the Business	Operational Management	.006	Reject	Significant
	Financial Management	.000	Reject	Significant
	Expenses Management	.004	Reject	Significant
Number of Employees	Operational Management	.002	Reject	Significant
	Financial Management	.000	Reject	Significant
	Expenses Management	.020	Reject	Significant

**Significant at .05 alpha level*

Table 7 shows the post hoc for nature of business. For operational management coping strategy, respondents under manufacturing and merchandising industries have higher value in using operational management coping strategy than those respondents in the service industries. For financial management coping strategy, respondents under the manufacturing and merchandising industries have higher value in using financial management coping strategy than those respondents in the service industries. For expenses management coping strategy, respondents in the manufacturing and merchandising industries have higher value in using expenses management coping strategy than those respondents with service nature of business.

Table 7. Post hoc for nature of business per coping strategy

Coping Strategy	Compared Values		p-value	Ho Decision	Significance
Operational Management	Manufacturing	Merchandising	.202	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
		Service	.004	Reject	Significant
Financial Management	Manufacturing	Merchandising	.566	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
		Service	.005	Reject	Significant
Expenses Management	Manufacturing	Merchandising	.000	Reject	Significant
		Service	.000	Reject	Significant
Expenses Management	Merchandising	Manufacturing	.219	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
		Service	.006	Reject	Significant
		Service	.000	Reject	Significant

**Significant at .05 alpha level*

Table 8 shows the post hoc for number of years in the business per coping strategy. For compared sub-level with significance under operational management coping strategy, those businesses with 13 to 15 years in the business and 10 to 12 years in the business have higher value in using operational management coping strategy than those businesses with one to three years in the business. Similarly, those businesses

with seven to nine years in the business shows higher value in using operational management coping strategy than those less than seven years in the business.

For financial management coping strategy, those businesses with 13 to 15 and 10 to 12 years in the business shows higher value in using financial management coping strategy than those businesses with one to three years. Those businesses with seven to nine and four to six years in the business shows higher value in financial management coping strategy than those businesses with one to three years, while those with seven to nine years in the business shows higher value in using financial management coping strategy than those businesses with four to six years. For expenses management coping strategy those businesses with seven to nine, 10 to 12, and 13 to 15 years in the business show significantly higher value in using expenses management coping strategy than those businesses with one to three years in the business.

Table 8. Post hoc for number of years in the business per coping strategy

Coping Strategy	Compared Values		p-value	Ho Decision	Significance
Operational Management	13 to 15	1 to 3	.018	Reject	Significant
	10 to 12	1 to 3	.018	Reject	Significant
	7 to 9	4 to 6	.014	Reject	Significant
	7 to 9	1 to 3	.000	Reject	Significant
Financial Management	13 to 15	1 to 3	.001	Reject	Significant
	10 to 12	1 to 3	.002	Reject	Significant
	7 to 9	4 to 6	.032	Reject	Significant
	7 to 9	1 to 3	.000	Reject	Significant
	4 to 6	1 to 3	.031	Reject	Significant
Expenses Management	13 to 15	1 to 3	.021	Reject	Significant
	10 to 12	1 to 3	.002	Reject	Significant
	7 to 9	1 to 3	.000	Reject	Significant

**Significant at .05 alpha level*

Table 9 shows the number of employees per coping strategy. Those businesses with six (6) to 10 employees have significant high value in using operational management coping strategies than those business with no employee, one to five employees, and 11 to 15 employees, respectively. Those businesses with six (6) to 10 employees show significantly higher value in using financial management coping strategy than businesses with no employees. Also, those businesses with six (6) to 10 employees show significantly higher value in financial management coping strategy than those with more than 10 employees and less than six employees. Those businesses with six (6) to 10 employees show significantly higher value in using expenses management coping strategy than those businesses with more than 10 employees and less than six employees.

Table 9. Post hoc for number of employees per coping strategy

Coping Strategy	Compared Values		p-value	Ho Decision	Significance
Operational Management	No Employee	6 to 10	.002	Reject	Significant
	1 to 5	6 to 10	.000	Reject	Significant
	6 to 10	11 to 15	.024	Reject	Significant
Financial Management	No Employee	1 to 5	.002	Reject	Significant
	No Employee	6 to 10	.000	Reject	Significant
	No Employee	11 to 15	.049	Reject	Significant
	No Employee	More than 15	.046	Reject	Significant
	1 to 5	6 to 10	.001	Reject	Significant
	6 to 10	11 to 15	.029	Reject	Significant
	6 to 10	More than 15	.031	Reject	Significant
Expenses Management	No Employee	6 to 10	.023	Reject	Significant
	1 to 5	6 to 10	.002	Reject	Significant
	6 to 10	11 to 15	.047	Reject	Significant

**Significant at .05 alpha level*

Business enterprises are exploring a new post-Covid-19 business model to recover from the negative effect of this devastating disease that causes financial crisis to them. Based on the findings of this study, the researcher is hereby proposing a business strategy model to cope with the negative impact of Covid-19.

Table 10. Financial, Operating and Expense Management (F.O.E.M) Coping Strategy Model

	Financial Management	Operating Management	Expenses Management
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stabilize finances and sustain operation of the business Manage cash flows 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Operate business continuously 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Balance expenses with income
Program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delay payment of bills Use personal savings as capital Leverage financial institution with cheapest interest rate 	Use alternative ways such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> E-commerce as distribution platform Social media as advertising platform E-logistics as delivery platform Home service Arrange a skeletal workforce and allowed work from home for employees focusing on online marketing / trading 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use substitute materials / ingredients that have cheaper costs in producing goods Minimize usage of utilities
Persons involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business owner 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business owner Employees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business owner Employees
Task	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The business owner should negotiate with creditor to extend payment of bills. The owner should sacrifice personal savings to cope the shortage of working capital. The owner should scout a financial institution with the least offered interest, for leveraging. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The business owner should create an online application to utilize the e-commerce, social media, and e-logistic in business marketing and trading. The business owner should create guidelines on the process of producing products and accepting orders up to delivering the products including the payment scheme. Employees should implement the strategies formulated by the business owners. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The business owner should canvass an alternative product or materials which has cheaper cost to substitute the existing product. The business owner should innovate. Employees should follow the guidelines created by business owner.
Output / Result	Financial stability	Business continuity	Balancing expenses

Conclusion and Recommendations

In terms of nature of business, the researcher believes that merchandising industries dominate most, because the market demand for products in the area of Bacoor is higher than the demand for services, compared to setting up a manufacturing industry. Theoretically, manufacturing industry needs a lot of money, time, and space than merchandising industry. In terms of form of business, most of the respondents

are sole proprietorship, because the researcher believes that it is the easiest business formation with regards to business requirements and capitalization than the partnership and cooperatives. In terms of the number of years in business, the respondents who are operating within the range of one to three years dominates most, because more people wanted to create their own businesses, since job vacancies are not as many as expected. In terms of the number of employees, most of the respondents have one to five employees because most of them are sole proprietors. Majority of the business owner-respondents rent their stores.

Business owners have very high level of operational management coping strategy to survive at this time of pandemic. This means that they reduced their production of goods including inventory stacking. They also shortened their operation hours and arranged a skeletal workforce for their employees. In addition, they used alternative ways to market their product and services by utilizing the online media platforms for trading and marketing and tapped the e-delivery services for the distribution of their products. Following health protocols was also implemented by the business owners.

Business owners have very high level of financial management coping strategy to get through at this time of pandemic. This means that business owners used their personal savings to cover the shortage of working capital. If personal savings is not enough, they borrowed from friends or relatives and the last source was the financial institution. They delayed the payments of bills with proper negotiation with the creditors. They also intensified collections through offering discounts to their account customers.

Business owners have very high expenses management coping strategy to keep businesses going at this time of crisis. This means that they reduced capital investment, minimized their usage of utilities, and controlled the daily operating expenses. They also considered buying cheaper products as substitute to the main product ingredients or materials used in the operation of their businesses.

Business owners perceived that operational management, financial management, and expenses management coping strategies are very effective in balancing expenses, cash flow, financial stability, business continuity and payables. This means that operational management coping strategy helped the business owners in maximizing revenue and minimizing expenses, maintaining a positive working capital for the business. Through this strategy, it also helped the business sustains its operation, and made the business survived during the time of pandemic.

Business owners who rent their stores have higher operational, financial and expenses management coping strategy than those who own business stores. Manufacturing and merchandising industries have higher operational, financial and expenses management coping strategy than those who are in service industries. Partnership have higher operational, financial and expenses management coping strategy than those sole proprietorship and cooperatives. Tenureship has something to do with the operational, financial and expenses management coping strategy. The more the business is tenured, the higher the operational, financial, and expenses management coping strategy. Businesses with six (6) to 10 employees have higher value in operational, financial and expenses management coping strategy.

Owners of the service industries could offer tangible products connected to their services (e.g. therapy oil for massage center; energy drinks or organic drinks for fitness center; beauty products for salon; dental kits for dental clinics). They should not rely on one product-line, they should innovate products that could be offered to the market. They could also offer home service and utilize the online media platform in providing instructional service and consultation service.

Owners of merchandising industries could arrange a scheme for skeletal workforce, and a work-from-home for other employees focusing on online marketing or trading. They could deploy their own employees for delivery products as long as an additional compensation is given as hazard pay. Also, innovate products that are suitable to customers who are staying at home.

Owners of manufacturing industries could use cheaper materials as substitute to their ingredients without prejudicing the quality of products they are producing. They could also produce products that are

more essential to customers during the times of pandemic. They could also arrange a scheme for skeletal workforce, and a work-from-home for other employees focusing on online marketing or trading.

The proposed business strategy model of the researcher can be used to address the problems encountered by the small business owners. The study relies on the data collected from small businesses in Bacoor, Cavite. The findings may not completely reflect the situation among the small industries. Therefore, a future study could explore the business strategies used by other industries to cope with the negative effect of Covid-19 among the small industries.

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